

RULE BOOK

ALTERNATIVE TRANSIENT PROGRAM

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XXIII - App	Appendix CABLE PARAMETERS supporting program	CP-1/27
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XXIII Appendix. **CABLE PARAMETERS Supporting Program**

Prof. Akihiro Ametani's separate program was added to ATP during the summer of 1994 as documented in Can/Am newsletters dated July and October, 1994. Such usage, illustrated within standard test cases DC-27 and DC-28, involves a CABLE PARAMETERS declaration immediately following the old CABLE CONSTANTS declaration. The following is an adaptation of the instructions for Prof. Ametani's self-contained program. The summary shall begin with Prof. Ametani's own description (text moved from Section I) --- slightly modified to suit ATP needs. About limits on number of conductors, most matrices are seen to be dimensioned (12,12), so the limit is believed to be 12 (temporarily fixed).

WSM + THL, 12 July 1995.

The ATP "CABLE CONSTANTS" routine had originally been developed from 1976 to 1981 by this author, Akihiro AMETANI (Professor at Doshisha University, Kyoto, Japan) under contract with Bonneville Power Administration, Portland, Oregon, U.S.A. Since then, a number of modifications have been carried out by various persons. Ametani has found it difficult for himself to trace all the modifications, and some of the calculated results are not correct. He has kept his own independent CABLE CONSTANTS which has been modified time by time by himself. He has started restructuring of his own CABLE CONSTANTS since October, 1993, and added new options into the program. The restructuring has been partially completed, and Ametani has decided to release the new program named CABLE PARAMETERS through the BPA as an all-new supporting program of ATP.

The structure and functions of the CABLE PARAMETERS are the same as those of CABLE CONSTANTS (see ATP Rule Book Chapter XXIII). The options of a stratified earth, which was rarely used, and the crossbonded cable, which was complicated to use, have been deleted in CABLE PARAMETERS. But several new options have been added:

- (1) Arbitrary cross-sectional shape for conductors;
- (2) Distributed shunt admittance model;
- (3) Transposition/snaking of a cable system.

Furthermore, the option of grounded conductors (parameter "NGRND") has been modified. The modified version of "NGRND" is completely different from that of "NGRND" in CABLE CONSTANTS.

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- I. Introduction

See the initial page, to which material of this section was moved.

II. General Description of the Program

II-1 Outputs

The "CABLE PARAMETERS" program can be used to calculate the following outputs of Class A: underground/overhead single-core coaxial cable (SC cable in Fig. 1 (a)), Class B: underground/overhead pipe-enclosed type cable (PT cable in Fig. 1 (b)) and Class C: overhead line (OH line in Fig. 1 (c)) as a function of frequency f .

Fig. 1 Various types of cables

- (1) series impedance $[Z] = [R] + j[X]$, $[X] = \tilde{u}[L]$ $[\tilde{U}/m]$
- (2) shunt admittance $[Y] = [G] + j[B]$, $[B] = \tilde{u}[C]$ $[S/m]$
- (3) characteristic impedance $[Z_0]$ $[\tilde{U}]$

- (4) transformation matrix (eigenvectors) [A] for voltage and [B] for current
- (5) modal quantities; attenuation constant $\hat{\alpha}$ [dB/km], propagation velocity v [m/ $\hat{\mathbf{i}}$ s], impedance Z [$\hat{\mathbf{U}}$ /m], admittance Y [S/m], characteristic impedance Z_0 [$\hat{\mathbf{U}}$], characteristic admittance Y_0 [S]
- (6) δ (PI) equivalent model of a cable or an OH line per unit length for ATP simulation
- (7) Ametani's distributed line model of a cable or an OH line per unit length : multiphase lossy line model with transformation matrix at a fixed frequency

II-2 Input Data

To calculate the above explained outputs, the following input data are required.

- (1) input/output specification; type of cable, i.e. OH line (Class C; ITYPE = 1), SC cable (Class A; ITYPE = 2) or PT cable (Class B; ITYPE = 3), etc. : corresponds to data card A3, B3, or C3 in CABLE CONSTANTS
- (2) \$PUNCH is used for punched cards just as with other supporting programs. See illustration in DC-27 and DC-28.
- (3) number of conductors, geometrical configuration and physical constants : corresponds to data cards A4 and A5 for SC cable, B4 to B7 for PT cable or C4 for OH line in CABLE CONSTANTS
- (4) shunt conductance and/or capacitance, which may represent boundary conditions of the conductors, to be defined by a user independently from the shunt admittance [Y] calculated by the program (term (2) of Sec. II-2) : data card A5+, B7+ or C4+
- (5) geometrical configuration of conductors to the earth : corresponds to data card A6, B8 or C5 in CABLE CONSTANTS
- (6) earth resistivity and frequency at which the outputs are to be calculated : corresponds to

data card A7, B9 or C6 called "Frequency Card" in CABLE CONSTANTS

III. CABLE PARAMETERS Data Cards

III-1 General Structures

The structure of a data case of "CABLE PARAMETERS" will depend upon which of the following three classes it falls into:

Class A : SC cable, system of single-core coaxial cables without enclosure

Class B : PT cable, system of SC cables within an enclosing pipe

Class C : OH line, system of conventional overhead lines

1. Class A Data Structure

- A1. First comes a "BEGIN NEW DATA CASE" card (actually optional, as per Section II-A).
- A2. Next comes a "CABLE CONSTANTS" card, followed by a "CABLE PARAMETERS" card. These serve to transfer control to the new code.
- A3. First comes a miscellaneous data card.
- A4. Next comes one (or possibly more) card upon which is keyed the number of conductors which make up each SC coaxial cable of the system. One card will suffice for a system of up to sixteen cables; two cards are required for 17-32 cables, etc.
- A5. Next comes two (or possibly three) cards of geometrical and physical data for each SC coaxial cable in the system. E.g., for three SC coaxial cables, a maximum of nine cards would be required.
- A6. Next comes one (or possibly more) card which gives the horizontal and vertical location of the centers of all SC coaxial cables in the system. A single card will handle up to four SC coaxial cables; two cards are required for 5-8, etc.
- A7. Last comes a frequency card, which specifies a new earth resistivity and frequency (or range of frequencies) for which cable constants are to be calculated.

2. Class B Data Structure

- B3. First comes a miscellaneous data card.
- B4. Next will come one card which gives parameters of the pipe.
- B5. Next will come one (or possibly more) card which specifies the location of each SC coaxial cable within the pipe. One card will suffice for up to 4 SC coaxial cables, two will be required for 5-8 SC coaxial cables, etc.
- B6. Next comes one (or possibly more) card upon which is keyed the number of conductors which make up each Sc coaxial cable of the system. One card will suffice for a system of up to sixteen cables; two cards are required for 17-32 cables, etc.
- B7. Next come two (or possibly three) cards of geometrical and physical data for each SC coaxial cable in the system. E.g., for three SC coaxial cables, a maximum of nine cards would be required.
- B8. Next comes one card which gives the horizontal and vertical location of the center of the pipe.
- B9. Last comes a frequency card, which specifies a new earth resistivity and frequency (or range of frequencies) for which cable constants are to be calculated.

3. Class C Data Structure

- C3. First comes a miscellaneous data card.
- C4. Next come three cards for each circuit which belongs to the overhead conductor system. Parameters specified include the number of phases, the number of ground wires, the number of conductors in a bundle, geometrical data, conductor resistivity, etc. E.g., considering a system which consists of a single-circuit 500 kV transmission line and a double-circuit 230-kV transmission line all on the same right of way, nine data cards would be involved.
- C5. Next comes one (or possibly more) data card which gives the height, sag, and horizontal location for the center of each bundle of each circuit of the system. One card will suffice for 1 or 2 bundles, two cards are required for 3 or 4 bundles, etc. E.g., two coupled single circuits, each of which is supported by its own towers and has a single ground wire, would require four cards (because there are eight bundles total -- four for each circuit).
- C6. Last comes a frequency card, which specifies a new earth resistivity and frequency (or range of frequencies) for which line constants are to be calculated.

2 : continuously transposed OH line

1.3 NPC

- (1) Classes A and B; number of SC cables which make up the system of interest. Example: NPC = 3; three-phase SC cable system (the most common case).
- (2) Class C; number of transmission circuits which make up the overhead line system of interest.

The numbers of phase wires and ground wires in a circuit are to be defined in data card "C4" (NP = number of phase wires, NG = number of ground wires).

1.4 IEARTH; not used, leave blank.

1.5 KMODE; flag used to request the calculation and output of various modal quantities of interest.

Presently it is fixed to "KMODE=1," and all the modal quantities described in Sec. II-1 (5) are calculated and printed.

1.6 IZFLAG; flag indicating intermediate printout.

IZFLAG = 0 : no intermediate printout
= 1 : intermediate printout

The format of the impedance and admittance printout is fixed to: $[R]$, $\tilde{u}[L] = [X]$, $[G]$ and $\tilde{u}[C] = [B]$, but not $[L]$ and $[C]$.

1.7 IYFLAG; not used, leave blank.

1.8 NPP

- (1) Class A....NPP = -99 : transposition (snaking) of SC cables
≠ -99 : unused
- (2) Class B....NPP = 1 : pipe of finite thickness
0 : pipe of infinite thickness (ISYST is automatically set to be zero.)
-1 : snaking of inner conductors (SC cables) for a finite thickness pipe (corresponding to NPP = 1)
-99 : snaking of inner conductors for an infinite thickness pipe (corresponding to NPP = 0)
- (3) Class C....unused

1.9 NGRND; This parameter describes the number of grounded conductors in an OH line (Class C) and a cable system (Classes A and B). (In CABLE CONSTANTS, NGRND

describes the grounding conditions of the cable system, and the value of NGRND does not correspond to the number of the grounded conductors.)

Grounding starts from the most outer conductor to the inner conductors for all the classes (Classes A, B and C) as illustrated in Fig. 2. At least, one conductor (a core of phase 'a' SC cable in Classes A and B, phase 'a' conductor in Class C) has to be left (not grounded).

Fig. 2 Example of grounded conductors for parameter "NGRND"

For Class C (OH line), when conductors 4 and 5 in the above figure are defined as a ground wire (GW; NP = 3, NG = 2 in data card C4-1 in Sec. 3), then the conductors 4 and 5 are automatically grounded and the conductor system is reduced to 3 x 3 from 5 x 5 independently from the parameter NGRND. In this case, thus, NGRND should be less than 3 ($NGRND \leq 2$). Also, the case with "NP = 3, NG = 2" gives the same result as the case with "NP = 5, NG = 0, NGRND = 2"; three conductors are left (not grounded).

1.10 IDATA; flag indicating the type of the input data "A5," "B7" and "C4." This parameter is a new one; it does not exist in CABLE CONSTANTS.

IDATA = 0: conventional circular (cylindrical) conductor, data input by radius and resistivity of the conductor

IDATA = 1: arbitrary cross-section conductor explained in Appendix 2, data input by cross-section area, outer surface length and dc resistance of the conductor

Parameters:

- RP1 : inner radius of the pipe [m]
- RP2 : outer radius of the pipe [m]
- RP3 : outer radius of the pipe outer insulator [m]
- \tilde{n}_p : resistivity of the pipe [\tilde{U} -m]
- \tilde{i}_p : relative permeability of the pipe
- \tilde{a}_{p1} : relative permittivity of the pipe inner insulator
- \tilde{a}_{p2} : relative permittivity of the pipe outer insulator

Fig. 3 A PT cable (figure at right)

Note: $R_{p1} < R_{p2} < R_{p3}$ in theory. Keep this condition independently from the parameter NPP and from a specific condition of a given PT cable. For example, even if a pipe has no outer insulator, it has a corrosion protective covering or produces a thin oxide-film, which is a kind of an insulator, and thus $R_{p2} < R_{p3}$. Also even if $NPP = 0$, give an arbitrary value for R_{p2} and R_{p3} keeping the condition $R_{p1} < R_{p2} < R_{p3}$, and an arbitrary (non-zero) value for \tilde{a}_{p2} .

P3.2 Format for B5 Data

This data card indicates the location of each inner conductor (SC cable) enclosed within a pipe in polar coordinates, i.e. " d_k " and " \tilde{e}_k " in Fig. 3. The reference to the angular position \tilde{e}_k (degrees) can be taken arbitrary, but it might be better to take the horizontal line as the reference and to measure positive angle as counter-clockwise.

READ (5,901) (DC(I), THC(I), I = 1, NPC)

1		2		3		4		5		6		7		8	
1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890
d ₁	\tilde{e}_1	d ₂	\tilde{e}_2	d ₃	\tilde{e}_3	d ₄	\tilde{e}_4								
E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1

Parameters:

- d_k : distance from the pipe center to the center of the k-th conductor [m]
- \tilde{e}_k : angular position of the k-th conductor to a reference line [deg.]

Note: - Since each SC coaxial cable needs one pair (d_k, \tilde{e}_k), one card can handle up to four cables.

cable).

READ (5,901) (RADI(I,J), J=1, NCPPK)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890
R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	R ₅	R ₆	R ₇
E10.1						

READ (5,901) (ROI(I,J), USR(I,J), USI(I,J), ESI(I,J), J=1, NCPPJ)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890
\bar{n}_c	\bar{i}_c	\bar{i}_{i1}	\bar{a}_{i1}	\bar{n}_s	\bar{i}_s	\bar{i}_{i2}	\bar{a}_{i2}
E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1

If the SC cable has armor, one more set of the data is required:

1	2	3	4
1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890
\bar{n}_a	\bar{i}_a	\bar{i}_{i3}	\bar{a}_{i3}
E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1

Fig. 4 SC cable cross-section

Parameters:

For a better understanding of all parameters involved, we refer to Fig. 4.

R1 : inner radius of the tubular core [m]
 = 0 for solid core

R2 : outer radius of the tubular core [m]
 (= inner radius of the first insulating layer)

R3 : inner radius of the sheath [m]
 (= outer radius of the first insulating layer)

R4 : outer radius of the sheath [m]
 (= inner radius of the second insulating layer)

R_5 : inner radius of the armor [m]
 (= outer radius of the second insulating layer)

R_6 : outer radius of the armor [m]
 (= inner radius of the third insulating layer)

R_7 : outer radius of the third (= outer most) insulating layer [m]

\tilde{n}_c : resistivity of the tubular core [\tilde{U} -m]

\tilde{i}_c : relative permeability of the tubular core

\tilde{i}_{i1} : relative permeability of the first insulating layer (in general, $\tilde{i}_{i1} = 1$)

\tilde{a}_{i1} : relative permittivity of the first insulating layer

\tilde{n}_s : resistivity of the tubular sheath [\tilde{U} -m]

\tilde{i}_s : relative permeability of the tubular sheath

\tilde{i}_{i2} : relative permeability of the second insulating layer (in general, $\tilde{i}_{i2} = 1$)

\tilde{a}_{i2} : relative permittivity of the second insulating layer

\tilde{n}_a : resistivity of the tubular armor [\tilde{U} -m]

\tilde{i}_a : relative permeability of the tubular armor

\tilde{i}_{i3} : relative permeability of the third insulating layer (in general, $\tilde{i}_{i3} = 1$)

\tilde{a}_{i3} : relative permittivity of the third insulating layer

O3, O4 Format for C4-1 and C4-2 data

It should be noted that an overhead line (OH line; Class C) is a special case of an overhead SC cable. Thus, an OH line parameter is calculated as an overhead SC cable parameter in this program and in CABLE CONSTANTS (i.g. ITYPE = 2, ISYST = 1 and NCPPk = 1 for k = 1 to NPC). Only bundles for phase and ground wires cause a difficulty to deal with the OH line as an SC cable. Because of the above, this program and the CABLE CONSTANTS program have the

following difference from the LINE CONSTANTS program.

1) It is important to note that the CABLE CONSTANTS code uses another technique than the LINE CONSTANTS code to take bundling into account. Whereas the LINE CONSTANTS code first calculates the line parameters for all individual conductors within a given bundle and then reduces the paralleled conductors to one equivalent phase, the CABLE CONSTANTS code will immediately handle the bundling (i.e. at input time), applying the geometric mean radius approximation for the bundle.

2) Furthermore, CABLE CONSTANTS assumes the following:

- Within one circuit, all "NP" phase-wire bundles count for the same number ("KNP") of individual physical conductors, all having the same geometry and physical data. All physical conductors within a bundle are uniformly spaced around the circumference of a circle.
- Within one circuit, all "NG" ground-wire bundles count for the same number ("KBG") of individual physical conductors, all having the same geometry and physical data. All physical conductors within a bundle are uniformly spaced around the circumference of a circle.
- Data are entered for the individual physical conductor, not for the bundle.

3) Finally, recall the sequence rule for overhead transmission line circuits:

- First take the circuit with the highest number NP (number of phase-wire bundles)
- Stop by taking the circuit with the lowest number NP (number of phase-wire bundles)

Hence, "NPC" (total number of circuits, see Sec. 1.3) sets of following three card formats need to specified next:

O.3 Format for C4-1 data

READ (5,901) (NCPJ(J), J=I1,I2)

1		2	
12345	67890	12345	67890
NP	NG	KBP	KBG
I5	I5	I5	I5

O.4 Format for C4-2 data

READ (5,901) (RADI(I,J), J=1, NCPPK)

1		2		3		4		5		6	
1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890
ROUT _p	RIN _p	ROUT _g	RIN _g	SEP _p	SEP _g						
E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1						

READ (5,901) (ROI(I,J), USR(I,J), J=1, NCPPL)

1		2		3		4	
1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890
\bar{n}_p	\bar{i}_p	\bar{n}_g	\bar{i}_g				
E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1				

Fig. 5. Illustrative single-circuit 3-phase overhead transmission line (as seen in cross-section). The three phase-wire bundles are of four conductors each; there are two ground-wire bundles, of three conductors each.

Parameters:

NP: The number of phase-wire bundles which belong to the circuit in question. E.g., for a 3-phase circuit, "NP" will equal three.

NG: The number of ground-wire bundles which belong to the circuit in question.

KBP: The number of individual physical conductors which compose each phase-wire bundle of the circuit in question. If there is no bundling of phase wires, "KBP" will equal unity, and leave SEP_p BLANK.

KBG: The number of individual physical conductors which compose each ground-wire bundle of the circuit in question. If there is no bundling of ground wires, "KBG" will equal unity, and leave SEP_g BLANK.

$ROUT_p$: outer radius of the individual tubular conductors which are used for each phase-wire bundle, see Fig. 6(a). [m]

RIN_p : inner radius of the individual tubular conductors which are used for each phase-wire bundle, Fig. 6(a). [m]
= 0 : solid conductor.

$ROUT_g$: outer radius of the individual tubular conductors which are used for each ground-wire bundle, Fig. 6(b). [m]

RIN_g : inner radius of the individual tubular conductors which are used for each ground-wire bundle, Fig. 6(b). [m]
= 0 : solid conductor

Fig. 6. Cross-section of a conductor

SEP_p : separation between the centers of two adjacent individual conductors within the phase-wire bundle. All 'KBP' conductors of the phase-wire bundle are supposed to be uniformly spaced around the circumference of a circle, see Fig. 7. [m]
= blank : no bundling (put $KBP = 1$).

SEP_g : separation between the centers of two adjacent individual conductors within the ground-wire bundle. All 'KBG' conductors of the phase-wire bundle are supposed to be

S_c	l_c	D_{i1}	S_s	l_s	D_{i2}	S_a	l_a
E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1

1
1234567890
D_{i3}
E10.1

READ (5,901) (ZY(I,J), USR(I,J), USI(I,J), ESI(I,J), J=1, NCPPJ)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890
R_c	\tilde{i}_c	\tilde{i}_{i1}	\tilde{a}_{i1}	R_s	\tilde{i}_s	\tilde{i}_{i2}	\tilde{a}_{i2}
E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1

1	2	3	4
1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890
R_a	\tilde{i}_a	\tilde{i}_{i3}	\tilde{a}_{i3}
E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1

Fig. 8 Cross section and physical constant of an arbitrary cross-section SC cable (Classes A and B)

Parameters (See Fig. 8.)

- S : cross-section area of conductor [m²]
- l : outer-surface length of conductor [m]
- D_i : average thickness of insulator [m]
- R : dc resistance of conductor [\tilde{V}/m]
- \tilde{i} : relative permeability of conductor
- \tilde{i}_i : relative permeability of insulator
- \tilde{a}_i : relative permittivity of insulator
- subscripts : c for core

- s for conducting sheath
- a for armor
- i for insulator
- 1 for insulator 1 (core to sheath)
- 2 for insulator 2 (sheath to armor)
- 3 for insulator 3 (armor outer)

For a cable consisting of a core and a sheath, 6 data expressing conductor cross-section ($S_c, l_c, D_{i1}, S_s, l_s$ and D_{i2}) and 8 data expressing physical constants ($R_c, \hat{i}_c, \hat{i}_{i1}, \hat{a}_{i1}, R_s, \hat{i}_s, \hat{i}_{i2}$ and \hat{a}_{i2}) are required. Thus 2 data cards rather than 4 data cards indicated above are necessary enough. When a cable is composed only of a core, 3 data for cross-section (S_c, l_c and D_{i1}) and 4 data for physical constants ($R_c, \hat{i}_c, \hat{i}_{i1}$ and \hat{a}_{i1}) are necessary enough.

O4A. Format for C4-2'

Data card C4-2' expresses the cross-section area, outer-surface length dc resistance and permeability of a conductor, and separation between conductors, while the data related to the above are expressed as the radii, resistivity and permeability in data card C4-2 as explained in Sec. O4.

```
READ (5,901) (DIJ(I,J), ANG(I,J), DIR(I,J), J=1, NCPPL)
```

1	2	3	4	5	6
1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890
S_p	l_p	SEP_p	S_g	l_g	SEP_g
E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1

```
READ (5,901) (ZY(I,J), USR(I,J), J=1, NCPPL)
```

1	2	3	4
1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890
R_p	\hat{i}_p	R_g	\hat{i}_g
E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1

Parameters (See Fig. 9.)

- S : cross-section area of conductor [m²]
- l : outer-surface length of conductor [m]
- R : dc resistance of conductor [\bar{U}/m]
- \hat{i} : relative permeability of conductor
- subscript: p for phase wire
- g for ground wire

Fig. 9 Cross-section and physical constant of an arbitrary cross-section conductor (Class C)

For an overhead line with no ground wire, leave BLANK for the data S_g , I_g , SEP_g , R_g and \hat{i}_g .

5. Format for A5+, B7+ or C4+ for IYG ≠ 0

..... New option for distributed admittance

When IYG ≠ 0, conductances and/or capacitances are to be defined by a user. The conductances and/or capacitances are added to the shunt admittances of a given cable or an overhead line which are evaluated automatically by the CABLE PARAMETERS or the EMTP CABLE CONSTANTS.

S5 = P5 Format for A5+ or B7+

READ (5,901) (YGI(I,J), J=1, NCPPJ)

1		2		3		4		5		6	
1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	
G(I,1)	C(I,1)	G(I,2)	C(I,2)	G(I,3)	C(I,3)						
E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1						

Parameters

G : conductance [S/m]

C : capacitance [F/m]

subscript I for phase 'I' of SC cables for Classes A and B

1 for core to sheath

2 for sheath to armor

3 for armor to earth (Class A) and pipe (Class B)

If an SC cables is consisting of a core and a sheath, the data G(I,3) and C(I,3) are left to be BLANK. See Fig. 10.

ITYG = 1 : G = 0 (BLANK) and C has to be defined.

2 : C = 0 and G has to be defined.

3 : G and C have to be defined.

Fig. 10 I-th SC cable consisting of a core and a sheath with a distributed admittance.

For a PT cable (Class B), the following data card is required right after the above data card for the last phase (i.e., after the last card):

READ (5,901) YG(NC,NC)

```

-----
|      1      |      2      |
| 1234567890 | 1234567890 |
|-----+-----|
|      Gp      |      Cp      |
|-----+-----|
| E10.1      | E10.1      |
|-----+-----|
-----
    
```

Parameters:

G_p : pipe conductance to be added [S/m]

C_p : pipe capacitance to be added [F/m]

O5 Format for C4+

READ (5,901) (YG(J,J), J=J1,NC), (YGI(I,J), J=1, J2)

```

-----
|      1      |      2      |      3      |      4      |      5      |      6      |      7      |      8      |
| 1234567890 | 1234567890 | 1234567890 | 1234567890 | 1234567890 | 1234567890 | 1234567890 | 1234567890 |
|-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----|
| G(I,1)      | C(I,1)      | G(I,2)      | C(I,2)      | G(I,3)      | C(I,3)      | ... Etc.    | ...      |
|-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----|
| E10.1      |
|-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----|
-----
    
```

```

-----
|      1      |      2      |      3      |      4      |      5      |      6      |      7      |      8      |
| 1234567890 | 1234567890 | 1234567890 | 1234567890 | 1234567890 | 1234567890 | 1234567890 | 1234567890 |
|-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----|
| ... Etc.    | ...      | G(I,NC)     | C(I,NC)     | Gg(I,1)  | Cg(I,1)  | ... Etc.    | ....      |
|-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----|
| E10.1      |
|-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----|
-----
    
```

Parameters

$G(I,k)$: conductance for phase wire 'k' [S/m]

$C(I,k)$: capacitance for phase wire 'k' [F/m] } $k = 1$ to NC

NC : total number of phase wires in circuit 'I'

$G_g(I,m)$ conductance for ground wire 'm' [S/m]

Parameters:

VERT_k : vertical distance (m) between the center of the k-th single-core coaxial cable and the earth surface. Always use POSITIVE values, no matter whether the system of cables is underground or in the air. This difference is made by flag ISYST (see point 1.2 in Sec. 1) on the miscellaneous data card.

HORIZ_k : horizontal distance (m) between the center of the k-th single-core coaxial cable and an arbitrary vertical reference line.

Fig. 11 Cable location

medium 1 = earth, medium 2 = air for ISYST = 1 and 0

medium 1 = air, medium 2 = earth for ISYST = -1

P6. Format for B8 data

This card gives the vertical location of the center of the pipe (which encloses all single-core coaxial cables of the system) with respect to the earth surface as illustrated in Fig. 11(b).

READ (5,901) (HI(I), DI(I), I=1, J1) ; J1=1

1	2
1234567890	1234567890

CENTER	Blank
E10.1	E10.1

Parameter:

CENTER : vertical distance (m) between the center of the pipe and the earth surface. Always use **POSITIVE** values, no matter whether the pipe is underground or in the air. This difference is made by flag ISYST (see miscellaneous data card).

O6. Format for C5 data

For each of the "NP" + "NG" bundles within each of the 'NCCT' circuits composing the overhead conductor system, a triplet of numbers giving the horizontal and vertical location (near tower and at midspan) of the center of the bundle is to be specified (see Fig. 12). At this stage of the data input, the variable expressing the number of circuits is 'NCCT' rather than 'NPC' which now expresses the total number of conductors. As for the order in which data have to be entered, following rules must be obeyed:

- First take all **phase-wire** bundles belonging to the circuit with the **highest** number of phase-wire bundles.

Fig. 12 Overhead line location

- Stop by handling the **phase-wire** bundles belonging to the circuit having the **lowest** number of phase-wire bundles.
- Next start handling the **ground-wire** bundles belonging to the circuit with the **highest** number of phase-wire bundles.

- Stop by handling the **ground-wire** bundles belonging to the circuit with the **lowest** number of phase-wire bundles.

This means:

- Keep the sequence of circuits, as specified in Sec. O3 and O4.
- First define the **phase-wire** bundle location, obeying the circuit sequence.
- Next define the **ground-wire** bundle location, obeying the circuit sequence.

READ (5,901) (HIH(I), HIL(I), DI(I), I=1, NPC)

1		2		3		4		5		6		
1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	1234567890	
Bundle #1 of this circuit						Bundle #2 of this circuit						... Etc. (one triplet for each bundle of circuit)
VTOWER ₁	VMID ₁	HORIZ ₁	VTOWER ₂	VMID ₂	HORIZ ₂							
E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1	E10.1							

Parameters:

VTOWER_k : vertical distance (m) near the tower, between the center of the k-th bundle and the earth surface.

VMID_k : vertical distance (m) at midspan, between the center of the k-th bundle and the earth surface.

HORIZ_k : horizontal distance (m) between the center of the k-th bundle and an arbitrary reference line.

NPC = total number of conductors at this stage, NCCT = number of circuits

NOTE: Since each bundle needs one triplet (VTOWER_k, VMID_k, HORIZ_k), one such card can handle up to two bundles.

7. Format for A7, B9 or C6

The "frequency card" of all three classes of data cases has the same format.

READ (5,905) ROE, FREQ, IDEC, IPNT, DIST

$k = 1, 2$	$k = 1, 2$	$k = 1, 2$
$n = 1$	$n = 2$	$n = 3 = \text{IDEC}$

(3) $\text{IPNT} = 3, \text{IDEC} = 3 ; f_{\text{begin}} = 2 \text{ Hz}, f_{\text{end}} = 10^3 \text{ Hz}$

$f = 2, 5, 10, 20, 50, 100, 200, 500, 10^3$

$k = 1, 2, 3$	$k = 1, 2, 3$	$k = 1, 2, 3$
---------------	---------------	---------------

$n = 1$	$n = 2$	$n = 3 = \text{IDEC}$
---------	---------	-----------------------

(4) $\text{IPNT} > 3 ; \Delta f = 10/\text{IPNT} = f_{\text{begin}}$

When $\text{IDEC} \times \text{IPNT} = 0$, the normal single frequency calculation is carried out. Independently from the above automatic looping, the cable or line parameters are calculated at the frequency "FREQ" given by the user.